

Oral manifestations of tuberculosis: tongue TB

Original Article

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INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis is a chronic infectious disease that can affect any part of the body including mouth. It usually affects the lungs, TB bacilli can spread hematogenous to other parts of the body including lymph nodes, meninges, kidneys, bone, skin and oral cavity involving the tongue with very unusual features and forms. It has been considered account for 0.1-5 % of all TB infections. These lesions are usually secondarily inoculated with infected sputum or due to hematogenous spread.

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OBJECTIVES:

To study the oral manifestations of tuberculosis- Tongue TB

Materials & Methods:

11 years old female presented with swelling over tongue for 2 weeks, gradually increasing in size. She also had complaints of low-grade fever and cough for 6 months, along with pain in abdomen, difficulty in breathing, reduced appetite, weakness and weight loss. Oral cavity examination showed a single ulcerating lesion over dorsum of the tongue with ill-defined margin, base of the ulcer was covered with slough with bleeding on palpation.

INVESTIGATIONS: Revealed

1.CBC : Hb - 7.7 TLC - 19110 , ESR : 24 mg/dl ,

2.CBNAAT FOR TB : Positive

3.USG THORAX : Significant pleural effusion along with collapse and consolidation of underlying lung.

4.ECHOCARDIOGRAPHY :

Gross pericardial effusion.

5.CECT ABDOMEN : Significant mesenteric lymphadenopathy (multiple, maximum size 25*20cm, conglomerated) with omental thickening.

6. PLEURAL FLUID : Straw colored and showed increased ADA levels.

7. TOTAL COUNTS: 5200 cells/mm³

8. FNAC TONGUE: could not be possible due to invasive procedure.

RESULTS

Based on the above findings, patient was labelled as a case of microbiologically confirmed disseminated tuberculosis with oral manifestations & ATT was started. Pericardiocentesis and other supportive management was also done. She responded on ATT and gradually her condition improved along with reduction in the size of tongue mass. In a cachexic patient presenting with non-healing tongue ulcers associated with either pleural effusion/pericardial effusion or consolidation in chest Xray, the possibility of tongue TB should be included in the differential diagnosis. Accurate diagnosis is critical for optimal treatment by focusing on the pathological source, to avoid in appropriate oral therapy.

CONCLUSION

Oral TB may occur at any location on the oral mucosa, but the tongue is most commonly affected. It may appear as ulcers, nodules, fissures, tuberculomas or granulomas. The most frequent lesion is a superficial ulcer, characterized by undermined edges, a granulating floor and occasional small tuberculous nodules around the periphery. Due to the rarity of oral TB, the diagnosis of these lesions usually become difficult as other lesions like aphthous ulcer, traumatic ulcer, syphilitic ulcer or squamous cell carcinomamimics the lesion. A detailed clinical history and examination are important to make up the diagnosis, ancillary studies including laboratory tests and radiological images are helpful although the tissue biopsy remains the golden standard for confirmation of diagnosis.